

TABLE I—EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS FOR ELECTROCHEMICAL PREPARATION OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Initial voltage V	Initial current A	Time of electrolysis h	Amount of metal dissolved g	Yield		E _f mol F ⁻¹
					g	%	
K ₂ [TiF ₆]	5	0.50	2.0	0.400	1.5	75	0.22
K ₂ [CrF ₆]	2	0.04	3.0	0.085	0.3	65	0.36
K[MnF ₆]	2	0.05	2.0	0.100	0.2	73	0.49
K ₂ [FeF ₆]	8	0.45	2.0	0.600	1.9	62	0.32
Cs ₂ [FeF ₆]	8	0.45	2.0	0.600	4.3	71	0.32
K[CoF ₆]	5	0.30	3.0	0.780	1.3	63	0.39
Cs[CoF ₆]	5	0.30	3.0	0.780	2.7	82	0.39
K[NiF ₆]	4	0.05	2.5	0.180	0.3	63	0.65
Cs[NiF ₆]	4	0.05	2.5	0.180	0.5	66	0.65

from aqueous solution. But the present method uses an aqueous medium at room temperature for all the compounds.

Experimental

The metals were in the form of rods or foils and were mostly 99.8% pure. Chromium and manganese were previously deposited on a platinum foil by electrolysis of their salt solutions and were subsequently used as anodes.

For the preparation of the complexes, electrolysis was carried out using a platinum foil (1 × 1 × 0.1 cm) as the cathode and the appropriate metals connected with platinum wire electrical leads as the anode. Aqueous HF (20%; 10 ml) was used for electrolysis. After electrolysis, the solutions were filtered to free from any disintegrated metal particles. The potassium and the caesium salts were precipitated by adding concentrated solutions of KF or CsF in HF (20%). The complexes were dried in a desiccator over KOH. The details of the experimental conditions are given in Table I.

Fluorine was analysed by titration with Th(NO₃)₄ after steam distillation of fluorosilicic acid⁶. Potassium and caesium were determined by AAS method. Other metals were determined by standard titrimetric or gravimetric methods.

Results and Discussion

Table I shows that fluorides of some 3d-metals can be easily prepared from aqueous HF at room temperature. The applied voltage was small (2–8 V) and the yield was very good (60–85% based on the amount of metal dissolved). The main reactions taking place at the electrodes are

These were evident from the observed electrochemical efficiency (number of moles of metal dissolved per Faraday of electricity passed). A slight deviation of the electrochemical efficiency (E_f) (Table I) from the theoretical value of 1/n was ascribed to disintegration of metal anode into fine particles, evolution of oxygen at the anode and slight fluctuation of current during electrolysis.

The compounds were characterised by chemical analysis, and the comparison of their magnetic moments^{4,7} and band positions in the electronic spectra^{4,8} with those given in the literature.

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An Attempt to Separate Bentonite and Alumina from their Binary Mixtures

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LONG-chain quaternary ammonium cations can replace the exchangeable cations present on certain clays, viz. montmorillonite, and the resulting clays have the important property of dispersion in a variety of organic solvents. Several workers have studied the change in the organophilic characteristics and other physical properties of organo-clay complexes¹⁻³ and

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